

Evaluation of Threat Elements of the Aydos (İstanbul) Population of the Endemic *Colchicum micranthum* Boiss. Species^A

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Abstract: *Colchicum micranthum* Boiss. is a species endemic to Istanbul and protected under the Bern Convention. This study evaluated the distribution and threat factors affecting populations of the species in Aydos Forest. Field observations conducted in 2022 recorded a total of 1120 individuals across five observation locations, with an estimated distribution area of 14,074.89 m² and a local density of 0.08 individuals m⁻². The findings revealed a fragmented population distribution, with recreational pressure, road maintenance, construction activities, and habitat fragmentation identified as major threats to the species. The results suggest that anthropogenic pressures may pose risks to Aydos populations and highlight the need for microhabitat conservation measures and regular population monitoring for the long-term conservation of the species.

Keywords: *Colchicum micranthum* Boiss., Endemic, Aydos forest, Conservation.

^AThe study does not require approval from an ethics committee. The article has been prepared according to research and publication ethics.

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Atif/Citation: Yıldırımtepe, İ. and Aktürk İsaoglu, C. 2026. Evaluation of threat elements of the Aydos (İstanbul) population of the endemic *Colchicum micranthum* Boiss. species. *Journal of Biological and Environmental Sciences*, 58, 20752081.

Introduction

Türkiye is one of the most important regions in terms of plant and vegetation diversity. The reason for this situation is Türkiye's geographical location, geological structure, the presence of diverse soil types, and varied macro and micro climate characteristics (Kocabaş, 2020). Türkiye is a region rich in biodiversity due to its location at the intersection of the European-Siberian, Mediterranean and Irano-Turanian phytogeographic regions (Davis, 1965). The flora of Türkiye comprises approximately 12,000 vascular plant taxa, about 32% are endemics (Güner et al., 2012). In recent years, Türkiye and the world have been facing global warming and climate change, which have become a real threat. According to some researchers, the Earth has entered a new geological era called the Anthropocene (Zalasiewicz et al., 2015), which is characterized by human-induced temperature increases and has great effects on natural and atmospheric processes (Parolly, 2015; Kougioumoutzis et al., 2020). As a result of this situation, it is expected that there will be changes that will significantly affect many ecosystems and the plant diversity in these ecosystems (Parolly, 2015). In addition to this global threat that affects Türkiye's plant diversity, factors such as unintentional removal from nature, destruction of forest areas, harmful effects of pesticides, fire, overgrazing, intrusive and unplanned urbanization also damage Türkiye's flora and cause the extinction of endemic species. Ekim *et al.* (2000) reported that 12 endemic species of Türkiye have become extinct.

İstanbul, Türkiye's most populous city, is the largest urban agglomeration in Europe with a population exceeding fifteen million (Tuncay and Akalın, 2018). Due to its soil diversity, geographical location between two continents and climate, İstanbul has an exceptional plant diversity with 2500 species (Özhatay et al., 2012). According to the list of Important Natural Areas, important plant areas containing endemic, rare or threatened plants and rare habitats in İstanbul are Terkos Coasts, Küçükçekmece Basin, West İstanbul Pastures, Ağaçalı Dunes, The Bosphorus, Kilyos Dunes, İstanbul Islands, Ömerli Basin, Pendik Valley, Şile Coasts (Doğa Derneği, 2006). Pendik Valley, one of these areas evaluated within the scope of Important Natural Areas, is a region located within the Pendik Gebze-Tuzla border at altitudes of 10 - 180 m in an area of 2852 ha. This region is under pressure due to industry, settlement and transportation facilities. Especially due to its proximity to Sabiha Gökçen Airport, the housing demand in that region has increased (Doğa Derneği, 2006). Urbanization, the development of transportation infrastructure, tourism, and other changes in land use pose significant threats to biodiversity, particularly in forest ecosystems under urban pressure. These pressures can lead to the fragmentation of natural habitats, the disruption of ecosystem continuity, changes in vegetation dynamics, and impacts on species composition (Himshikha et al., 2022). In regions under severe human pressure, such as İstanbul, these impacts are becoming increasingly critical both for the integrity of forest ecosystems and for the survival of endemic species with limited ranges.

Aydos Forest, one of the important natural areas in the Pendik Valley, serves as a major green space for the surrounding urban area. This is one of the remaining sections of the Northern Forests that has managed to survive despite urbanization. It is located on the Anatolian side of İstanbul, and is a "B" type recreation area with two main areas: Aydos Hill and Aydos Pond (Erdem, 2019). Aydos Castle and Aydos Pond, one of the symbols of Aydos, have become recreation areas because of their view, nature variety, and clean air. For these reasons, it is a very popular place to visit.

Aydos Forest has large plant populations and different kinds of wild animals. Notably, it is home to several endemic plant species that are only found in Türkiye, specifically İstanbul. One of the endemic species distributed in Aydos Forest is *Colchicum micranthum* Boiss. According to the Illustrated Flora of Türkiye Volume II, C.

micranthum is a species that is distributed only in İstanbul in Türkiye (Güner et al., 2018). *C. micranthum* is a cormose plant also known as "Narin Acıçığdem" in Turkish. It blooms from August to October and is found in Kılıçpınar and Kestane Suyu, Kurtköy, Pendik, Samandıra and Aydos, Yakacık, and the foothills of Mount Aydos (Güner et al., 2018). *C. micranthum* belongs to the Colchicaceae family and grows in the Black Sea phytogeographic region. It grows in maquis, forest clearings and moist meadows (Güner et al., 2018). *C. micranthum* has a semi-spherical to ovoid, upright corm structure. The flowers of the species form a funnel-shaped perigon tube. Tepals oblanceolate to elliptic, veined, white to pale pinkish-purple, without dots, apex rounded to truncate (Figure 1 – A and B). Filament is white or ivory-white, anther is yellow. Style is white, stigma is decurrent (Güner et al., 2018).

Figure 1. *Colchicum micranthum* Boiss. in Mount Aydos. A- General view, B- Flower (Photographs by Ceren AKTÜRK, 2022).

Colchicum species are highly valuable medicinal plants because they have been used to treat many diseases like gout, inflammation, and cancer (Gülsoy Toplan et al., 2016). It is known that the biological importance of *Colchicum* species comes from the tropolonic alkaloids they contain, especially Colchicine (Gülsoy Toplan et al., 2016). *Colchicum* species also contain flavonoids, phenolic acids, tannins, and fatty acids (Evans, 2002). As a member of the genus *Colchicum*, *C. micranthum* is valuable for the phytochemicals it contains such as Colchicine, Colchifoline, 2-demethyl-colchicine, N-deacetyl-N-formylcolchicine (Gülsoy Toplan et al., 2018) besides its importance to biodiversity.

Areas where the plant is naturally found, especially Aydos Forest, are used as recreation areas by the public during the flowering periods (August to October) of the plant. Unintentional damage by visitors as a result of the area being used as a recreation area threatens the breeding potential of the species. Based on these data, it is very important that the plant be protected within its distribution area.

As a comparable example, *Crocus olivieri* subsp. *istanbulensis* B. Mathew, another endemic taxon occurring in the region, is protected by Sultanbeyli Municipality. It seems that some attempts have been made to help

recognize the plant to protect it. These initiatives include using the image of the plant as the municipality logo and organizing awareness-raising events such as festivals to promote the plant. In this context, there are no studies on the protection or recognition of the *C. micranthum*. These studies are very important for the protection of biodiversity. Of course, the conservation of the *C. micranthum* species, which is reported to have medium levels of colchicine content (Gülsoy Toplan et al., 2018), is valuable in terms of the phytochemical content of this species being used as a medicinal source in the future. At this point, informative data about the *C. micranthum* species is needed, as is the case with the *Crocus olivieri* subsp. *istanbulensis*.

In this study, it is aimed to determine the threats to the Aydos forest population of the *C. micranthum* species, which is naturally distributed only in İstanbul. Within the scope of this study, it is also aimed to determine the situation of individuals in the region, to provide information around the region and to carry out studies that will form the basis for the protection of this species in its natural habitat.

Materials and Methods

In this study, the current status of the *C. micranthum* species, found in the Aydos region, one of its distribution areas in İstanbul, was investigated through field observations. Fieldwork was conducted between July 2022 and November 2022. At the beginning of the fieldwork, preliminary observations were made in the study area, and the locations where the species was found were identified. Since the species exhibited a fragmented distribution within the study area, individual counts were conducted in the areas where the species was detected during field observations. Anthropogenic impacts resulting from the region's use as a recreational area and its proximity to residential areas were observed and documented with photographs during field observations. The species' distribution within the study area was determined based on the location data of the observation points. The observation points were marked on Google Earth, and the species' approximate distribution area was delineated by connecting the outermost boundary points.

Figure 2. Study site in Aydos recreation area (marked in red).

Results and Discussion

According to the field observations of this study, the areas most heavily used by the public in the Aydos Forest are around Aydos Pond and Aydos Castle. The field observations revealed that *C. micranthum* was not found around Aydos Pond and Aydos Castle. In the areas marked in red, *C. micranthum* populations were found in patches extending to the roadside and forest boundaries (Figure 2). A total of 1120 individuals were counted in the observed locations. The total distribution area was determined as 14,074.89 m² based on recorded observation points. Accordingly, the local density within the observed patches was 0.08 individuals m².

This density value represents the approximate local density within the identified distribution area. Similarly, density expressions in terms of individuals m² have also been used in population studies of other *Colchicum* species (Smith, 2004; Mróz, 2006; Adriaens et al., 2009). Wehsarg (1929) noted that in *Colchicum autumnale* L., individuals may exhibit a scattered distribution in meadows with short vegetation, in young populations, or in populations mowed when seeds have matured but leaves are still green. This situation has been linked to the limitation of vegetative reproduction, and it has been suggested that the scattered distribution may be due to generative reproduction (Wehsarg, 1929). These observations provide an ecological framework for interpreting the patchy distribution pattern observed in *C. micranthum*. Furthermore, the local distribution findings for *C. micranthum* are consistent with the lower range of density variation reported for *Colchicum hungaricum* Janka, a relict endemic species (Fenyósi et al., 2026). However, this density value alone is not sufficient to draw conclusions about the long-term health or sustainability of the population; such an assessment requires demographic structure and long-term monitoring data.

The first thing that stands out about the distribution areas of the populations is the absence of any signs or information indicating that the plant is endangered and needs protection. Within the scope of this study, it was determined that there is unintentional human-induced damage in the areas where the plant spreads. When the observed threats are evaluated, the unintentional removal of individuals from nature, the crushing of individuals as a result of barbecues and picnics within the species' distribution area, and the littering in the region and the resulting pollution are noteworthy (Figure 3). All these factors physically damage this endemic plant, which occurs in a restricted area, during its flowering and fruiting periods, seriously threatening the reproductive continuity of the species.

Figure 3. Threatened *Colchicum micranthum* individuals in the recreation area in Aydos (Photographs by Ceren AKTÜRK, 2022).

Apart from the unintentional damage caused by the public using the plant's distribution area as a recreation area, the facilities established in the possible distribution areas of the species in the forest attract attention. In addition to existing facilities, construction activities in the region's forested areas are also limiting the potential range of this species. In this context, it was determined that situations such as unplanned asphaltting works, road maintenance works, and new facility works damaged the spread of the plant (Figure 4). It has been shown that forest roads can alter light and soil conditions by creating edge effects, influence the composition of understory plant communities, and exert pressure on plant population dynamics (Avon et al., 2010). These effects could also pose a potential threat to *C. micranthum* populations, which are small and fragmented.

Figure 4. Potential distribution area and threat factors of *Colchicum micranthum* (Photographs by Ceren AKTÜRK, 2022).

It is well known that small and fragmented populations are more vulnerable to habitat fragmentation and human-induced edge effects. It has been reported that habitat fragmentation has negative impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem functions, particularly in small and isolated patches, and that these effects can intensify over time (Haddad et al., 2015). From the perspective of conservation biology and forest ecosystem management, it is important not only to identify threats to small and fragmented populations but also to develop species-focused habitat management approaches. Götmark (2013) proposes a “species management” approach based on the conservation of microhabitats, particularly for threatened species, in forest areas of high conservation value. In this context, the conservation of sensitive microhabitats for *C. micranthum*, the restriction of non-forestry-related interventions, and area management practices aimed at reducing visitor pressure can contribute to the long-term conservation of the species.

As an endemic species with a limited distribution range, *C. micranthum* is highly sensitive to environmental degradation and human-induced pressures. The results of this study indicate that populations in Aydos Forest are relatively small, confined to fragmented areas, and have low population density. Field observations have revealed that recreational activities pose significant threats to the species. Furthermore, infrastructure development and increased concreting in forest areas can lead to habitat loss and fragmentation, further limiting the species' potential range.

The monitoring of *C. micranthum* populations and the identification of existing threat factors are of great importance for the development of effective conservation strategies, given that it is a species protected under the Bern Convention and is also pharmacologically significant. Increasing public awareness, implementing protective measures in sensitive habitats, and limiting human activities in the species' distribution areas can contribute to the long-term conservation of this endemic plant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of this study highlight the importance of protecting *C. micranthum* populations in Aydos Forest. Given the increasing anthropogenic pressures in the region, protective measures must be taken to ensure the long-term sustainability of the species. To increase public awareness and prevent unintentional damage to populations, it is recommended that informative signs be placed in recreational areas, especially where the species is found. Furthermore, responsible institutions and local authorities should take appropriate conservation measures to protect the species' natural habitats.

In particular, to reduce recreational pressure during the species' vegetative growth and flowering period (August–October), the development of microhabitat conservation plans is recommended; concrete conservation measures such as the installation of temporary fencing in sensitive areas, the restriction of visitor access, and the rerouting of pedestrian traffic to alternative paths are proposed.

Protecting the remaining habitats of *C. micranthum* in Aydos Forest is crucial for ensuring the long-term conservation of this endemic species.

Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

Acknowledgements

This research was financially supported by TÜBİTAK through the 2209-A University Students Research Projects Support Program (Project No. 1919B012108098). The authors sincerely thank TÜBİTAK for its support.

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